

ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET – AUSTRIAN CASE STUDY

Public payments:

41% - CAP Pillar one, with:

40% - Basic Scheme Payment, and/or Single Farm Payment, and/or Single Area Payment
1% - coupled subsidies

59% - CAP Pillar two, with:

14% - Less Favoured Area (LFA) payments
12% - Subsidies for organic farming
23% - Other agri-environmental and climate change payments (without forestry payments)
10% - Other rural development payments (e.g., for physical investments, modernisation, quality standards)

Characteristics of the case study areas

Farm, farm-group and territorial scale

LIFT large-scale farmer survey in AT

- Steyr-Kirchdorf (AT314)
- Salzburg & Umgebung (AT323)
- Farm type: Specialized dairy farms
- n = 94 farms (total): 52% AT314 & 48% AT323
- n = 81 farms (available for economic analysis)

Perceived missing knowledge and missing skills regarding management of ecological farming practices, in %

	All	Steyr-Kirchdorf	Salzburg und Umgebung	Organic	Standard
Absolutely disagree	32	40	28	36	31
Disagree	43	40	45	48	38
Neutral	18	16	19	9	25
Agree	6	4	6	5	6
Absolutely Agree	1	0	2	2	0

Source: LIFT large-scale farmer survey; n=94

Dairy farms in Austria according to the levels of adoption of ecological approaches (farm shares, %)

*The case-study specific classification of ecological farming approaches took into account regional production systems (haymilk TSG – associated with integrated (circular) farming of the LIFT farm typology, organic farming and a combination of haymilk TSG and organic farming).

Livestock feed (average feeding months)

Selected indicators of farm technical-economic performance

Profitability indicators – Revenue Cost Ratios (RCR)*

Efficiency*

*A ratio larger than 1 indicates farms can cover their costs with their revenues. The terms public and private refer to the inclusion or exclusion of public payments from revenues. Costs of own production factors (land, labour capital) were calculated based on estimated opportunity costs (imputed wage for unpaid labour, imputed rent for own land and imputed interest rate for equity).

*Efficiency values reflect performance of farms relative to benchmark farms (i.e. how well farms use their inputs (land, labour, capital intermediate expenses) to produce different outputs (see names of the four efficiencies). A value of 1 indicates full efficiency. Efficiencies were estimated with Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA).

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ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET - BELGIAN CASE STUDY

Case study characteristics:

Permanent crops, arable and mixed crops-livestock systems located in the southeastern part of Flanders. Hilly region highly prone to erosion.

35% of farmers receive AES subsidies

5% are organic farmers

30% are arable farmers

57% have mixed crops and livestock systems

Average UAA per farm is 55 ha

80% of farmers produce grains, 63% produce maize, and 43% produce energy crops

19% of farmers engage in cooperative land rotation

32% of farmers make use of on-farm contract work

Cooperative behaviour amongst farmers:

- 19% of farmers engage in cooperative land rotation
- 32% of farmers make use of on-farm contract work

Previous experience with cooperative behaviour was found to have a significant positive effect on farmer preferences to engage in labour, knowledge and machinery sharing.

Ecological agriculture

Agri-environmental performance normalised to a 0-1 scale

Currently most applied

- Mulching
- Cover crops
- Green manure
- Crop rotation
- Integrated pest management
- Grass strips

Most expected in future

- Integration of semi-natural landscape elements
- Agroforestry
- Low external input systems
- Use of organic fertilizers

Hageland-Haspengouw

Public preferences for aesthetic landscape features associated with ecological farming

- People prefer large energy generating infrastructures (e.g., solar panels and large wind turbines) over small infrastructure
- People dislike large farm buildings and heavy mechanisation
- People prefer landscapes with crop dividers, either managed or unmanaged, to no crop dividers
- People dislike monoculture landscapes, preferring at least a medium-level of diversity
- People prefer land to remain covered between cropping cycles by cover crops or crop residue

Large wind turbines (>25m high) and solar panels throughout the landscape

Parcels remain covered by a cover crop between seasons

Low mechanization (only manual labour)

High landscape diversity (livestock and multiple crop types)

Clear managed crop dividers

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KU LEUVEN

ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET - FRENCH CASE STUDY

Puy-de-Dôme, Ille-et-Vilaine, Sarthe (France)

Survey to 229 farmers

For year 2018
62% dairy farms

Payments received

Average share of payments for farmers

- 40.4%** - Basic Scheme Payment or Single Farm Payment
- 22.9%** - Less Favoured Area (LFA) payments
- 12.5%** - Coupled Subsidies
- 12.0%** - Non-EU public subsidies (State, local government)
- 10.2%** - Subsidies for organic farming
- 1.7%** - Other agri-environmental and climate change payments (without forestry payments)

Fertilisation and soil management

Share of farmers depending on percentage of crop area covered by practice

Farmers' opinion on collective-based policies

Agree that collective efforts should be rewarded ('Reward') but not keen on actually participating in a scheme with a collective aspect ('Participation')

Share of farmers – Opinion on 4 statements:

- (1) Result: "The environmental impact of my uptake of an ecological practice can be impeded by my neighbours' decisions"
- (2) Participation: "I am keen to participate in an agri-environmental scheme in which the amount of subsidy I receive depends on both me and my neighbours' uptake of new practices"
- (3) Cost: "I can think of ecological practices for which adoption by a sufficient share of neighbouring farmers would lower my cost of adoption"
- (4) Reward: "Collaborative efforts in the adoption of ecological practices between neighbouring farmers should be rewarded"

Farmers' opinion on changes in working conditions when transitioning

From more conventional to ecological practices

France (metropolitan)

Farm ecological types based on LIFT protocols

FADN data 2015

Stakeholders' vision for ecological farming in 2030 in the 3 case study areas

- Consumers will not buy a lot more of their food locally.
- The nature of work on farms will be more physically demanding.
- There will be no change in trade of locally sourced inputs.
- Farmers will need to increase their level of skills.
- Water quality will improve.
- 10% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices.

Large share of marketed output through cooperatives
55% for milk in France

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ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET – GERMAN CASE STUDY (UPPER BAVARIA)

Agri-environmental payments:

- 13%** - EU Payments linked to Natura 2000 and the Water Framework Directive.
- 37%** - Other rural development payments (e.g., for physical investments, modernisation, quality standards).
- 12%** - Subsidies for organic farming.
- 22%** - Less Favoured Area (LFA) payments.
- 16%** - Other agri-environmental and climate change payments.

Characteristics of the case study area

Source map: www.firmendb.de

Bavaria represents 20% of Germany's area. The average size of Bavarian farms is 47 ha, but only 27.7 ha in Upper Bavaria. Bavaria is one of Germany's leading regions in terms of organic farming: in 2021, 13% of Bavarian agricultural land was organic. The case study region of Upper Bavaria makes ca. 25% of the total area of Bavaria. 45.3% of Upper Bavaria are under agricultural use (33.7% is forest). Nearly two thirds of the farms in Upper Bavaria (64%) focus on forage production or pasture farming (dairy cows).

Share of organic certified agricultural land in Bavarian districts in 2021 (in %):

Source: Datengrundlage: SIMELF 2021 Geobasisdaten: © Bayer. Vermessungsverwaltung (www.geodaten.bayern.de)

Percentages above are official data of the rural development program for the funding period 2014-2020 and show planned payments for Bavaria. Only payments from the second pillar of the CAP (Common Agricultural Policy) were taken into account. The following payments were not considered: Basic Scheme Payment, and/or Single Farm Payment, and/or Single Area Payment, Non-EU public subsidies (State, local government), Coupled Subsidies, Forestry Payments.

In total, 51 farmers participated in the LIFT large-scale farmer survey. In 2018 ca. 17% of the surveyed farms were organic and about 15% of the interviewees were female farmers. The average size of all surveyed farms was 66 ha and the median size was 57 ha, which is much larger than the average farm size in Upper Bavaria.

The uptake of ecological approaches by the surveyed 51 Bavarian farms is shown in the graph on the right. As some farms can be classified as belonging to several categories, the different circles are intersecting. More than half of the farms (29) are putting the system of conservation agriculture into practice (brown circle). This is partly due to the nature of the sample analysed. The majority of these farms are either dairy farms or have a mixed farming system, namely animals and arable cropping. As the graph shows, 8 farms are organic farms (green circle).

Categorisation of surveyed farms in Upper Bavaria based on LIFT typology protocols

Germany (51 farms)

IMPACT OF NEIGHBOURING FARMERS ON ECOLOGICAL PRACTICES

Source: Ecozept on basis of a face-to-face survey on 51 farms located in Upper Bavaria. The survey was conducted from May to August 2019 with a standardised questionnaire. The sampling was done by Ecozept out of a group of 107 farmers already working on water conservation projects.

In the LIFT large-scale farmer survey the farmers have been asked to what extent the following statements describe their attitude and beliefs. They were asked to choose between five possible answers ranging from "strongly agree" (green bar) to "strongly disagree" (red bar in the left graph). The following statements have been assessed by surveyed farmers:

- a) "Collaborative efforts in the adoption of ecological practices between neighbouring farmers should be rewarded".
 - b) "I can think of ecological practices for which adoption by a sufficient share of neighbouring farmers would **lower my cost of adoption**".
 - c) "I am keen to participate in an agri-environmental scheme in which the amount of subsidy I receive **depends on both me and my neighbours'** uptake of new practices".
 - d) "The environmental impact of my uptake of an ecological practice can be impeded by **my neighbours' decisions**".
- The farmers agree especially on item (b) and are likely to adopt ecological practices if the related costs are lowered by a sufficient share of neighbouring farmers (ca. 70% of farmers agree "somewhat" or "strongly").

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ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET – GREEK CASE STUDY

Farmers' views on Agri-environmental payments

Should CAP Pillar I direct payments be more tightly linked with mandatory requirements on the adoption of ecological practices?

Type of environmental requirements that should be mandatory to receive Pillar I direct payments (% of farmers)

Average total pesticide costs = € 1,082
Average total fertilizer* costs = € 787
Total output = € 24,224

Pesticide intensity index
(Pesticide costs/Total Output) = **0.0447**

Fertiliser* intensity index
(Fertiliser* costs/Total Output) = **0.0325**

*inorganic

Case study area: East Crete

Farm, farm-group and territorial scale

Case study areas:
East Crete – Regional Units
of Heraklion & Lasithi
(GR)

Landscape features and habitats (UAA) in Heraklion case study

Landscape features and habitats (UAA) in Lasithi case study

EAST CRETE (GR)

Distribution of olive and wine farms in East Crete according to the levels of adoption of ecological approaches (farm shares and numbers)

N=108

* Farms showing the highest level of adoption of ecological practices in the case study sample
** Standard farms

Respondents' views on the farm practices an ecological farm would use as opposed to a conventional farm

Respondents' views on the vision for ecological farming in 2030 regarding...

Interconnected ecological farms

- As a proportion of household income, income from farming will decrease
- 50% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices
- Consumers will not buy a lot more of their food locally
- 10% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices
- Farmers will need to increase their level of skill
- Ecological farms will form clusters of closely connected farms within the area

Less agreed upon statements → Most agreed upon statements

Environment & eco-system services

- 10% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices
- As a proportion of household income, income from farming will decrease
- Consumers will not buy a lot more of their food locally
- The wider rural economy will be more resilient
- Water quality will improve
- There will be tight certification to define farms as ecological

Less agreed upon statements → Most agreed upon statements

Skills and labour

- The wider rural economy will become more resilient
- Ecological farming will be a limited social movement and will not provide substantial eco-system services
- More livestock farmers will use mob/strip grazing
- There will be more need for migrant labour
- Farmers will need to increase their level of skill
- There will be tight certification to define farms as ecological

Less agreed upon statements → Most agreed upon statements

Respondents' views on how the adoption of ecological farming would impact on the following aspects

Fertilisation and soil management (UAA) in Heraklion case study

Fertilisation and soil management (UAA) in Lasithi case study

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ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET - HUNGARIAN CASE STUDY

Data from the LIFT large-scale farmer survey in Hungarian case studies (120 farms in Hajdú-Bihar and Veszprém)

Production types of surveyed farms

- Specialist cereal, oilseed and protein crops
- Specialist horticulture
- Specialist wine
- Specialist orchards (excluding olives)
- Other

Surveyed farms according to the levels of adoption of ecological approaches (based on LIFT typology protocol)

Fertilisation and soil management of crop area in surveyed farms

Features of utilised agricultural areas (UAA) in surveyed farms

- Hedgerows
- Bushes
- Wet areas
- Tree lines
- Woodland on UAA (coppice, afforested areas, woodlots, etc.)
- Isolated trees
- Field margins
- Buffer strips
- Flower strips
- Terraces
- Other

Case study areas: Hajdú-Bihar and Veszprém (Hungary)

Stakeholders' opinion on predicted rate and pattern of adoption of ecological practices in Veszprém

- Low adoption rate - clustered
- Low adoption rate - random

Stakeholders' views on the vision for ecological farming in 2030

Hajdú-Bihar and Veszprém

- 50% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices
- There will be more demand for female labour for manual operations
- The nature of work will be more physically demanding
- Farmers will need to increase their level of skills
- There will be tight certification to define farms as ecological
- There will be little change in the landscape appearance of rural areas

Least agreed upon statements Most agreed upon statements

Hajdú-Bihar

- 50% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices
- The nature of work will be more physically demanding
- Employment opportunities in farming will increase
- Farmers will need to increase their level of skills
- There will be little change in the landscape appearance of rural areas
- There will be tight certification to define farms as ecological

Least agreed upon statements Most agreed upon statements

Veszprém

- 50% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices
- There will be more demand for female labour for manual operations
- Little change will happen to soil quality
- Farmers will need to increase their level of skills
- There will be tight certification to define farms as ecological
- The farmer's daily routine will become more varied

Least agreed upon statements Most agreed upon statements

Stakeholders' views on how the adoption of ecological farming would impact on labour (part 1)

Stakeholders' views on how the adoption of ecological farming would impact on labour (part 2)

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IRWIR PAN

ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET - IRISH CASE STUDY

Agri-environmental payments:

- 57.5%** - Basic Scheme Payment, and/or Single Farm Payment, and/or Single Area Payment;
- 19%** - Subsidies for organic farming;
- 10.3%** - Other agri-environmental and climate change payments (without forestry payments);
- 7.1%** - Less Favoured Area (LFA) payments;
- 6%** - Other rural development payments (e.g., for physical investments, modernisation, quality standards);
- 0%** - Coupled subsidies;
- 0%** - non-EU public subsidies (state, local government).

Characteristics of the case study area - Ireland

Organic lowland pasture-based beef farms predominantly located in Border, Midland and West region.

Ireland

Farms in Irish beef sector according to the levels of adoption of ecological approaches (farm shares, %) based on LIFT farm typology protocol

Note: Farm ecological types are based on 385 Irish beef farms in 2015 Farm Accountancy Data Network data, while other figures in the factsheet are based on LIFT large-scale farmer survey data.

Livestock disease management practices

Livestock feed (average feeding months)

Manure and slurry management practices

Grazing system

- Local rotation around farm
- Seasonal movement (stay in summer rangelands, spend grazing on mountainous rangelands)

Grazing period

- Average number of days grazing
- Average number of days indoor

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ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET - ITALIAN CASE STUDY

Agri-environmental Payments (based on 100 surveyed farms):

- 1% - EU Payments linked to Natura 2000 and the Water Framework Directive
- 30% - Other rural development payments (e.g. for physical investments, modernisation, quality standards)
- 75% - Basic Scheme Payment, and/or Single Farm Payment, and/or Single Area Payment
- 8% - Subsidies for organic farming
- 8% - Less Favoured Area (LFA) payments
- 57% - non-EU public subsidies (State, local government)
- 15% - Other agri-environmental and climate change payments (without forestry payments)

Case study areas: Emilia-Romagna and Ravenna

Experts' views on the farm practices an ecological farm would use as opposed to a conventional farm

- Machine weeding
- Strip grazing
- Extensive use of cover crops
- Integration of crop and livestock at farm level
- Alternative remedies for livestock disease management**
- Number of crops
- Precision technologies
- Integrated Weed Management
- Integrated Pest Management
- Low tillage use
- Use of organic manure or compost

Emilia-Romagna and Ravenna (IT)

Farms according to the levels of adoption of ecological approaches in Emilia-Romagna (based on FADN 2010-2013 data, farm shares, %)

Survey results:

Average total pesticide costs = € 5580
 Average total fertiliser costs = € 2826
 Average total output: € 138,924

Pesticide intensity index
 (Pesticide costs / Total Output)
 = **0.0887**

Fertiliser intensity index
 (Fertiliser costs / Total Output)
 = **0.0431**

Respondents' views on the vision for organic farming in 2030 (Q-SORT and DELPHI)

Statement Num.	Statements
1	50% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices.
2	10% of farms in the case study area will adopt ecological farming practices.
3	Ecological farms will form clusters of closely connected farms within the case study area.
4	There will be little change in the landscape appearance of rural areas.
5	Water quality will improve.
6	Little change will happen to soil quality.
7	There will be no change in the number and/or size of hedgerows.
8	Employment opportunities in farming will increase.
9	The need for labour work of an individual farmer will be spread throughout the year.
10	The farmer's daily routine will become more varied.
11	The wider rural economy will be more resilient.
12	Farmers will need to increase their level of skills.
13	The nature of work on farms will be more physically demanding.
14	Farmers will cooperate more with neighbouring farmers and farms close to them.
15	Consumers will not buy a lot more of their food locally.
16	Ecological farming will be a limited social movement and will not provide substantial eco-system services.
17	There will be tight certification to define farms as ecological.
18	As a proportion of household income, income from farming will decrease.
19	More livestock farmers will use mob/strip grazing.
20	Mob/strip grazing decreases the requirement for labour.
21	Rural areas will become no more attractive for residents and users.
22	There will be more need of seasonal labour.
23	The use of family labour will decrease.
24	There will be more need of migrant labour.
25	There will be no change in trade of locally sourced inputs.
26	There will be more demand for female labour for manual operations.

- ← Most disagreed upon statements | Most agreed upon statements →
- Little change will happen to soil quality.
 - There will be no change in trade of locally sourced inputs
 - Ecological farming will be a limited social movement and will not provide substantial eco-system services.
 - Farmers will need to increase their level of skills.
 - The wider rural economy will be more resilient.
 - Farmers will cooperate more with neighbouring farmers and farms close to them.

- ← Most disagreed upon statements | Most agreed upon statements →
- 50% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices.
 - Ecological farms will form clusters of closely connected farms within the case study area.
 - The nature of work on farms will be more physically demanding.
 - Farmers will need to increase their level of skills.
 - Rural areas will become more attractive for residents and users.
 - There will be no change in the number and/or size of hedgerows.

Experts' opinion on how the adoption of ecological farming would impact the following aspects

Experts' opinion on future of ecological farming systems

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ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET – POLISH CASE STUDY

Poland: Podlaskie and Lubelskie

Drivers for uptake of ecological approaches to farming

Average total pesticide costs = € 7870
Average total fertiliser costs = € 2203
Total output: € 400,088

Pesticide intensity index
(Pesticide costs / Total Output) = **0.0196**

Fertiliser intensity index
(Fertiliser costs / Total Output) = **0.0055**

Livestock Feed (Cattle)

- Grazing on pasture
- Conserved forage: silage
- Conserved forage: hay
- Concentrates
- Grains
- Beets
- Grazing on crop residues
- Other

Agri-environmental payments:

- EU Payments linked to Natura 2000 and the Water Framework Directive
- Other rural development payments
- Basic Scheme Payment, and/or Single Farm Payment, and/or Single Area Payment
- Subsidies for organic farming
- Less Favoured Area (LFA) payments
- non-EU public subsidies (State, local government)
- Coupled Subsidies
- Other agri-environmental and climate change payments (without forestry payments)

Dairy farms in Poland according to the levels of adoption of ecological approaches (based on FADN 2015 data)

- Agroecological
- Integrated/circular
- Organic
- Low-input
- Standard

Respondents' views on the vision for organic farming in 2030

Interconnected ecological farms

- Employment opportunities in farming will increase.
- 10% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices
- 50% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices
- Farmers will need to increase their level of skill
- Consumers will not buy a lot more of their food locally
- There will be tight certification to define farms as ecological.

Environment & eco-system services

- Little change will happen to soil quality.
- The wider rural economy will be more resilient
- As a proportion of household income, income from farming will decrease
- Water quality will improve
- Consumers will not buy a lot more of their food locally
- Ecological farms will form clusters of closely connected farms within the case study area.

Skills and labour

- The use of family labour will decrease.
- There will be more need for migrant labour
- There will be no change in trade of locally sourced inputs.
- Farmers will need to increase their level of skill
- There will be more demand for female labour for manual operations.
- There will be more need of seasonal labour.

← Less agreed upon statements Most agreed upon statements →

← Less agreed upon statements Most agreed upon statements →

← Less agreed upon statements Most agreed upon statements →

Fertilisation and soil management (UAA) Lubelskie crop area

Fertilisation and soil management (UAA) Podlaskie crop area

- Soil mapping
- Precision technologies to target application rate
- Planting of catch crops
- Leaving crop residues on soil
- Application of soil amendments
- Application of sewage sludge and other sludge
- Application of inorganic fertilisers
- Conservation tillage
- Machine controlled application
- Planting of cover crops
- Planting of nitrogen-fixing crops
- Green manuring
- Application of compost
- Application of animal manure
- No tillage
- Conventional tillage

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IRWIR PAN

ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET – ROMANIAN CASE STUDY

Agri-environmental Eligible areas (Suceava county, % in total agricultural area):

36.9% - Areas facing natural or specific constraints – Mountain areas

40.9% - HNV and traditional agricultural practices

9.8% - important meadows for butterflies (Maculinea Sp.)

5.3% - agricultural lands important as feeding ground for the lesser spotted eagle (Aquila Pomarina).

Source: Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, 2020

Characteristics of Case Study

Farm, Farm-group and territorial scale

Benefits, triggers and barriers – What effect has adoption of ecological farming practices had on the following outcomes?

(Based on LIFT large-scale farmer survey)

(Likert scale, where 1 represents a large decrease, and 5 – large increase)

SUCEAVA (RO)

Ecological farms versus standard farms – Dornelor Basin, Suceava CS, based on LIFT large-scale farmer survey

Dimension	Ecological farms	Standard farms
Average age of farm head	• 52 years	• 49 years
Average number of permanent workers	• 2	• 2
Average number of seasonal workers	• 3	• 1
Average number of hours worked per week by the farm head	• 53 hours	• 42 hours
Share of agricultural income in total household's income	• 68%	• 45%
Number of animals per hectare (LSU/Ha)	• 0.69 LSU	• 0.42 LSU
Share of farms where traditional cattle breeds are raised	• 75%	• 25%
Average number of grazing days	• 161 days	• 182 days
Share of farms that use summer camps for livestock	• 75%	• 35%

Livestock feed (dairy cows)

Respondents' views on the vision for ecological farming in 2030 (Q-SORT and Delphi)

Suceava county case study

3 least/most agreed statements (Z score)

Future of ecological farming system in Suceava CS -opinions of participants in Delphi exercise

Statement Num.	Statements
1	50% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices.
2	10% of farms in the case study area will adopt ecological farming practices.
3	Ecological farms will form clusters of closely connected farms within the case study area.
4	There will be little change in the landscape appearance of rural areas.
5	Water quality will improve.
6	Little change will happen to soil quality.
7	There will be no change in the number and/or size of hedgerows.
8	Employment opportunities in farming will increase.
9	The need for labour work of an individual farmer will be spread throughout the year.
10	The farmer's daily routine will become more varied.
11	The wider rural economy will be more resilient.
12	Farmers will need to increase their level of skills.
13	The nature of work on farms will be more physically demanding.
14	Farmers will cooperate more with neighbouring farmers and farms close to them.
15	Consumers will not buy a lot more of their food locally.
16	Ecological farming will be a limited social movement and will not provide substantial eco-system services.
17	There will be tight certification to define farms as ecological.
18	As a proportion of household income, income from farming will decrease.
19	More livestock farmers will use mob/strip grazing.
20	Mob/strip grazing decreases the requirement for labour.
21	Rural areas will become no more attractive for residents and users.
22	There will be more need of seasonal labour.
23	The use of family labour will decrease.
24	There will be more need of migrant labour.
25	There will be no change in trade of locally sourced inputs.
26	There will be more demand for female labour for manual operations.

Fertilisation and soil management practices on grassland

Origin of organic fertilisers

ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET - SWEDISH CASE STUDY

Agri-environmental payments (based on 184 surveyed farms):

- 0% - EU Payments linked to Natura 2000 and the Water Framework Directive
- 0% - Other rural development payments (e.g., for physical investments, modernisation, quality standards etc)
- 41% - Basic Scheme Payment, and/or Single Farm Payment, and/or Single Area Payment
- 5% - Subsidies for organic farming
- 18% - Less Favoured Area (LFA) payments
- 0% - non-EU public subsidies (State, local government)
- 21% - Coupled Subsidies
- 10% - Other agri-environmental and climate change payments (without forestry payments)

LIFT case study areas

Certified organic production at county level

Source: Swedish Board of Agriculture

Top counties with certified organic production

Source: [KRAV, Sweden](http://KRAV.Sweden)

SWEDEN (SE)

Respondents' top 14 sustainability objectives in the Plain areas of South Sweden

Livestock feed Sweden

Farm type: 70% grazing; 20% crop and livestock; 10% other

Average total pesticide costs = € 9000
Average total fertiliser costs = € 3500
Total output: € 400,000

Pesticide intensity index
(Pesticide costs / Total Output)
= **0.023**

Fertiliser intensity index
(Fertiliser costs / Total Output) =
0.009

Respondents' views on the vision for organic farming in 2030

Sweden (Plain areas of South Sweden)

Sweden (Plain areas of South Sweden)

Use of chemical fertilisers in South Sweden (% of UAA)

Use of chemical and organic fertilisers in North Sweden (% of UAA)

Statement Num.	Statements
1	50% of farms will adopt ecological farming practices.
2	10% of farms in the case study area will adopt ecological farming practices.
3	Ecological farms will form clusters of closely connected farms within the case study area.
4	There will be little change in the landscape appearance of rural areas.
5	Water quality will improve.
6	Little change will happen to soil quality.
7	There will be no change in the number and/or size of hedgerows.
8	Employment opportunities in farming will increase.
9	The need for labour work of an individual farmer will be spread throughout the year.
10	The farmer's daily routine will become more varied.
11	The wider rural economy will be more resilient.
12	Farmers will need to increase their level of skills.
13	The nature of work on farms will be more physically demanding.
14	Farmers will cooperate more with neighbouring farmers and farms close to them.
15	Consumers will not buy a lot more of their food locally.
16	Ecological farming will be a limited social movement and will not provide substantial ecosystem services.
17	There will be tight certification to define farms as ecological.
18	As a proportion of household income, income from farming will decrease.
19	More livestock farmers will use mob/strip grazing.
20	Mob/strip grazing decreases the requirement for labour.
21	Rural areas will become no more attractive for residents and users.
22	There will be more need of seasonal labour.
23	The use of family labour will decrease.
24	There will be more need of migrant labour.
25	There will be no change in trade of locally sourced inputs.
26	There will be more demand for female labour for manual operations.

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ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET – ENGLAND (UK) CASE STUDY

Agri-environmental payments (% of total subsidies):

- 1% - Subsidies for organic farming
- 10% - Other agri-environmental and climate change payments
- 3% - Other rural development payments (e.g., for physical investments, modernisation, quality standards etc)
- 82% - Basic Payment Scheme
- 4% - Coupled Subsidies

Characteristics of the case study areas

Farm, farm-group and territorial scale

Fertilisation and soil management (UAA) in High Weald

Fertilisation and soil management (UAA) in North Kent

High Weald and North Kent (UK)

Ecological vs Standard Farms

Farm Characteristic	Ecological farms	Standard farms
Farm size (Land area, ha)	355.62	222.10
Farm size (Livestock units)	94.69	25.99
Value of farm machinery (€)	277741.38	335000.00
Inorganic pesticide use (€/ha)	100.02	172.38
Inorganic fertiliser use (€/ha)	68.45	129.95
Organic animal manure or compost (% land area)	15.69	20.38
Crop diversity (number of different crops)	6.00	4.8
Semi-natural habitats (% land area)	6.90	6.67
Average hours of labour used (per farm, per week)	99.21	109.68

*Ecological farms defined as being organic and/or receiving agri-environmental subsidies

Limesurvey report for KENT University – constructive variables

Average total pesticide costs = € 73,411.5
Average total fertiliser costs = € 52,167.29
Total output: € 490,212.40

Pesticide intensity index (Pesticide costs/Total Output) = 0.15

Fertiliser intensity index (Fertiliser costs/Total Output) = 0.11

Livestock feed (Cattle)

Respondents' views on the vision for ecological farming in 2030

High Weald & North Kent

- Little change will happen to soil quality
- There will be no change in the number and/or size of hedgerows
- Ecological farming will be a limited social movement and will not provide substantial eco-system services
- Farmers will need to increase their level of skills
- Water quality will improve
- Farmers will cooperate more with neighbouring farmers and farms close to them

Least agreed upon statements → Most agreed upon statements

High Weald

- Little change will happen to soil quality
- There will be no change in the number and/or size of hedgerows
- Ecological farming will be a limited social movement and will not provide substantial eco-system services
- Water quality will improve
- More livestock farmers will use mob/strip grazing
- Farmers will need to increase their level of skills

Least agreed upon statements → Most agreed upon statements

North Kent

- There will be no change in the number and/or size of hedgerows
- Little change will happen to soil quality
- There will be little change in the landscape appearance of rural areas
- Farmers will need to increase their level of skills
- Water quality will improve
- Ecological farms will form clusters of closely connected farms within the case study area

Least agreed upon statements → Most agreed upon statements

Respondents' views on how the adoption of ecological farming would impact on labour

High Weald predicted rate and pattern of adoption

North Kent predicted rate and pattern of adoption

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ECOLOGICAL FACTSHEET – SCOTLAND (UK) CASE STUDY

FARM TYPES IN SCOTLAND ACCORDING TO THE ADOPTION OF ECOLOGICAL PRACTICES (FADN 2015)

Low-Input

Integrated/
Circular

Organic

Standard 79% (10210)

Number of farms in Scotland classified as one or more ecological type. Established using relative values from across EU 2011-2015 in FADN data and weighted for 2015.

Scotland Statistics:

- Scotland has just over 51,000 agricultural holdings;
- 35% cattle & sheep farms;
- 46% cereals & general cropping;
- 88% land is classified as LFA;
- Just under 60% of agricultural land is rough grazing.

Source: Scottish Government (2017)

Scottish LIFT large-scale farmer survey sample:

- 113 agricultural holdings;
- 81% had livestock, 28% had crop land, 15% had both;
- 82% classified as LFA;
- 93% of sample had some permanent grassland, 60% of which was grazed only.

Source: LIFT large-scale farmer survey (2018)

ADOPTION OF ECOLOGICAL PRACTICES – EVIDENCE FROM LIFT LARGE-SCALE FARMER SURVEY

Uptake of ecological livestock practices in Scottish case study versus other LIFT case studies

Uptake of ecological crop practices in Scottish case study versus other LIFT case studies

ATTITUDES TO ECOLOGICAL FARMING – EVIDENCE FROM LIFT LARGE-SCALE FARMER SURVEY

Environmental attitudes in Scottish case study versus other LIFT case studies

Environmental attitudes in Scottish case study versus other LIFT case studies

STAKEHOLDER PRIORITY SUSTAINABILITY OBJECTIVES

Eastern Scotland

Highlands and Islands of Scotland

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